

THE CURRENT STATE OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF NATIVE LANGUAGE SYNTAX BASED ON MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article describes the methodology for teaching the syntax section of primary school teachers of general secondary education.

Абстрактный. В данной статье рассказывается о методике преподавания раздела синтаксиса учителей начальных классов общего среднего образования.

Keyword. education, training, teaching methods, syntax, future teachers, state educational standards.

Ключевое слово. образование, обучение, методика обучения, синтаксис, будущие учителя, государственные образовательные стандарты.

The relevance of this topic is associated primarily with the change in the goals of teaching the Russian language and the emergence of fundamentally new requirements for the results of mastering the educational program by younger students, provided for in the State Educational Standard for Primary General Education in this subject, as well as with the methodological achievements of a number of advanced teachers who, as a result of their professional activities have a constant impact on the content, planning and organization of lessons and extracurricular activities in elementary school, in particular, they affect the usual forms and methods of teaching the syntax of the Russian language to younger students.

According to the State Educational Standard for Primary General Education, in elementary school (systematic course) 47 hours are allocated for the study of syntax, during which the entire system of work on the study of phrases and sentences should be aimed at the formation of certain subject educational actions in primary school students [3; 15]:

- the ability to compare sentences, phrases, words, naming their similarities and differences;
- the ability, with the help of semantic questions, to establish a connection between words in sentences and phrases;
- the ability to find narrative, motivating, interrogative sentences in the text;

- the ability to classify sentences according to the purpose of the statement;
- the ability to find sentences with certain characteristics in the text;
- the ability to determine the boundaries of sentences, as well as choose the sign of the end of a sentence;
- ability to explain ways of finding the main members of the proposal;
- the ability to find in the text and compose independently sentences with homogeneous members;
- the ability to explain in a sentence with homogeneous members the choice of the desired union;
- the ability to make a number of homogeneous members of the sentence and continue it.

With a sufficiently high level of formation of the listed subject learning activities, primary school students will be able to quite successfully achieve the planned subject results of mastering syntax.

The section “Syntax and punctuation” in the mandatory minimum content of primary general education consists of the following subsections [1; 34]:

- Phrase.
- Offer. The purpose of the statement, intonation.
- Sentences are narrative, interrogative, motivating.
- Punctuation at the end of a sentence.
- Members of the sentence: main (subject and predicate) and secondary (without division into types).
- Homogeneous members of the proposal. Unions and, but, but with homogeneous members of the proposal. Punctuation marks for homogeneous members of a sentence.

One of the most important tasks for the lessons of the Russian language is the formation in primary school students of the ability to consciously use phrases and sentences to express their own thoughts.

Therefore, in elementary school, work on these syntactic units occupies a special place, since it is on the syntactic basis that phonetics, morphology, vocabulary and, of course, spelling are taught. For younger students, the sentence helps to firmly understand the meaning of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and pronouns in the language.

Work on phrases and sentences, as we see, occupies a central place in teaching the syntax of the Russian language.

The issues of studying syntax in primary school in the methodological literature of the modern period are considered in the works of such researchers-

methodologists as: Л.В. Закожурникова, Н.А. Щербакова, И.В. Прокопович and others.

In elementary school, when working on a proposal, five directions are conditionally singled out [4; 68]:

1. work on the formation of the grammatical concept of "sentence" (consideration of the essential features of the proposal);
2. work on mastering the structure of a sentence by younger students (understanding the connection of words in a sentence, the role of main and secondary members, common and non-common sentences).
3. work on the formation of junior schoolchildren's skills to use in their speech sentences that are different in purpose and in intonation.
4. work on the skills of the exact use of words in a sentence.
5. work on the formation of skills to formulate sentences in writing.

All five identified areas of work on the study of syntax in elementary school actively interact with each other. For example, the study of a sentence and the formation of the ability to use it in speech is based on the constant expansion of elementary schoolchildren's actual knowledge of syntax.

Work on the theme "Offer" in elementary school continues during all four years of study. Primary school students during their studies in this matter move from elementary ideas about a sentence as several interconnected words expressing a common idea, to understanding the role of main and secondary members, to studying sentences with homogeneous members, common and non-common sentences, etc. .

The teaching material on the basics of syntax in primary school is studied in such a way that work on a sentence throughout the school year permeates other topics, although the volume of syntactic material for younger students is quite small. The main principle in mastering the concept of "sentence" is the development of the correct idea of the members of the sentence in younger students: students must learn that all members of the sentence are divided into two groups (main and secondary).

But in the primary grades of the traditional education system, the secondary members of the sentence are not differentiated into circumstance, definition and addition, and for the assimilation of this topic, only the very essence of the main and secondary members is revealed: the structural basis of the sentence is the main members, which take on the main semantic load, and the secondary members of the sentence perform a clarifying function. In the modern system of

teaching syntax to younger students, a general idea of specific types of secondary members is already provided.

Also, in parallel with the study of syntax in the primary grades, there is also an acquaintance with the basics of punctuation, the subject of which is the setting of four punctuation marks: a period, a question mark, an exclamation point, a comma. The setting of the last sign is limited to the study of a simple sentence with homogeneous members. Although the volume of punctuation rules considered in elementary school is slightly small and mainly “serves” the end of a sentence, the teacher should still work on punctuation, based on their general purpose in written speech. In addition, one of the important conditions that ensures the effectiveness of work on the elements of syntax and punctuation in elementary school is the integration of reading and Russian lessons. Younger students will quickly learn to read expressively, relying on their own knowledge of syntax, which provides conscious command of the sentence in oral and written speech. To obtain such results in the section "Syntax and Punctuation", it is effective to use a methodically verified system of exercises aimed at achieving particular goals of teaching syntax.

In general, depending on the degree of independence and cognitive activity of younger students, exercises on the topic "Syntax" are divided into three main groups [2; 29]:

1. Exercise based on the sample.
2. Constructive exercises.
3. Creative exercises.

Pattern-based exercises and constructive exercises involve the practical assimilation of clear, well-formed syntactic constructions. A significant place among the exercises of these groups belongs to analytical, as well as observation, listening and reading sentences. Drawing up proposals according to the model (based on imitation of the model) in various versions also belongs to the same group of exercises.

Creative sentence exercises assume the absence of any patterns: younger students must make sentences completely freely. The types of tasks for creative proposal writing may be limited to the topic for the proposals to be composed; a visual object for making sentences (making sentences on a picture), a few key words that should be used in the sentences being composed.

The most valuable are creative exercises in the preparation of sentences in the system of speech development. But, in comparison with exercises according to the model and constructive exercises, they have a significant drawback: since

the results of the work of a younger student in the first two types of tasks can be objectively measured: whether the proposed proposal meets the tasks set, whether the assignments for the proposals are completed correctly, etc. .

For creative exercises, there are no such criteria, but it is necessary to understand that the creative composition of sentences only makes significant sense when it proceeds at the highest level of the student's capabilities, that is, it is important for students to form high-quality skills when working with the word.

Thus, the study of syntax in elementary school presents many difficulties that the teacher must be able to overcome by forming the above-mentioned learning skills in the field of syntax and punctuation at a high level in younger students.

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